

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

FUSARIOSIS DISEASE SPREAD AND PATHOLOGY DEVELOPMENT INDEX IN ALFALFA

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Abstract

The presented is devoted to the study of ecological and biological characteristics of *Fusarium* species that infect different varieties of alfalfa from cultivated fodder plants and the fusariosis pathologies caused by them. It was determined that 7 species of *Fusarium* genus: *F.avenaceum* (Fr) Sacc., *F.gibbosum* APP. et Wr., emend Bilai, *F.solani* (Mart) App.et.Wr., *F.oxysporium* Schlecht. Emend Sndv. Et Hans., *F.sambucinum* App.et Wr, *F.bullatum* Sherb., *F.redolens* Bilai are found in the cultivated alfalfa plant. At the same time, it became known that if the Fusariosis disease recorded in alfalfa is caused by not one, but several species of fusariosis fungi, then the course of the pathology becomes more acute. Also, it was clarified that fusariosis disease is observed in all stages of the alfalfa plant vegetation period.

Keywords: alfalfa plant, eco-biological characteristics, vegetation period, the process of photosynthesis, fusariosis pathology, pathology development index.

Introduction: Various fungal genera participate in the structural organization of the pathomycobiota of fodder plants. Among these fungi, the species belonging to the genus *Fusarium* have a wide range of distribution and appear in quite variable biological forms [1; 8]. These fungi lead both saprotrophic and parasitic lifestyles, depending on the conditions encountered in the development process. The disease caused by fungi belonging to the genus *Fusarium* in fodder plants is usually called fusariosis. Fusariosis pathology settles on fodder plants and manifests itself as seed rot, root rot, leaf wilting, etc. It should be noted that the main source of fusariosis disease is soil [5; 6]. The causative agent of the disease, which enters the soil through the remains of infected plants, is directly involved in the transmission of the fusariosis disease is hidden at first, in the second half of the plants vegetation period, the intensity of the pathology increases and the level of virulence increases considerably. As a result, this leads to the reduction of the productivity of fodder plants up to 2 times, as well as to the deterioration of the quality of both the green mass and the seeds [2; 3].

Objective. If we take into account that our Republic is an agrarian country and the cultivated areas of plants are expanding every year, then there is a need to study the growth of species of fungi belonging to the genus *Fusarium* and the diseases caused by them in the lands where these plants are planted and in the cultivated fodder plants.

Material and methods: Forage farms located in Bilasuvar and Saatli districts were selected as a conventional experimental area for conducting research. Various varieties of alfalfa, including Absheron, Lider, Goyazan, black alfalfa, red alfalfa, etc.

Samples were taken from both soil and infected plants. At this time, more attention was paid to areas with a high background of infection. Planned route and

stationary observation methods, which are widely used in mycology, were used for sampling. It should be noted that sampling was carried out in different seasons of the year and in different phases of the alfalfa plant vegetation period. In the course of the research, in total, 800 samples of different varieties of alfalfa were taken and mycological examinations were carried out [4; 7; 9].

Results obtained and their discussion: It was determined that the following species belonging to the genus fusariosis were recorded in the alfalfa plant infected with Fusariosis disease: *F.avenaceum* (Fr) Sacc., *F.gibbosum* APP. et Wr., emend Bilai, *F.solani* (Mart) App.et.Wr., *F.oxysporium* Schlecht. Emend Sndv. Et Hans., *F.sambucinum* App.et Wr, *F.bullatum* Sherb., *F.redolens* Bilai.

Humidity factor has a direct effect on the intensity of fusariosis disease. Thus, high rainfall in the environment increases the level of humidity, which slows down the overall development of the alfalfa plant and the process of seed formation. As a result, initial symptoms of fusariosis are observed in both vegetative and generative organs of clover. In which a thin layer of hairy covering is observed on this or that organ infected with fusariosis, and the process of rotting begins in the tissues located at the bottom of it.

It turned out that when alfalfa sprouts, root rot with fusariosis is recorded for the first time. At this time, the infected roots first turn dark brown and gradually turn black. Fusariosis disease then spreads to the plants vegetative organs, including branches and leaves, where the infected areas first turn whitish and gradually turn pink. Consistent observations show that fusariosis rot disease is observed in all stages of the alfalfa plants vegetation period. It should be noted that *Fusarium solani*, *F.sambucinum*, *F.gibbosum*, *F.redoles* fungi are mainly involved in the pathology of

root rot with fusariosis. However *F.avenaceum* and *F.bullatum* fungi are found on vegetative organs, including branches. On the leaves, *F.oxysporium* fungus spreads more widely and causes wilting disease. At the same time, the analysis of the leaves infected with fusarium disease was also carried out according to the layer in the plant body. It was found that fusarium disease is 15-40% in the lower and middle layers of the

alfalfa plant, while it is more widespread in the upper layers, that is, in the leaves located in the upper part of the plant, and it is 50-75%. In addition, the pathology development index also showed different results. Thus, if the P.I.E is stable and obtained between 10-20% in the leaves of the lower middle layer, this indicator (parameter) increases in the leaves and becomes equal to 20-30% in the upper layer (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of Fusariosis disease in leaves of alfalfa by layers

In our opinion, both the rate of disease spread and the pathology development index are high in the upper tier leaves due to the fact that the photosynthesis process is more intensive in the upper tier leaves. The plant organism infected with fusariosis disease weakens from a physiological point of view, loses its turgor state, and necrotic changes occur in the vegetative organs.

Conclusions. As a result of the research conducted, it was found that fusariosis disease is usually caused by a type of fungus in fodder plants. However, fusariosis pathology can also be caused by a forest species belonging to the genus *Fusarium* and in this case, the etiology of the disease becomes more acute.

In the prevention of fusariosis pathology recorded in fodder plants, first of all, clean and pure seeds should be used as planting material. Because of this, the soaking of alfalfa seeds with TMTD and fundazol products of different concentrations, which are chemical preparations, gives effective results and productivity increases up to 2 times.

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